

NANOCOMPOSITE FOAMS BASED ON RENEWABLE RESOURCES SYNTHESISED FROM PICKERING EMULSION TEMPLATES

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SUMMARY

It is possible to stabilise Pickering medium internal phase emulsions (Pickering-MIPes) of modified soybean oils having internal aqueous phase levels above 60% solely with hydrophobised bacterial cellulose nano-fibrils. Such emulsions can be used as emulsion templates for the synthesis of porous polymer foams, so-called poly-Pickering-MIPes if the components of the continuous phase are polymerisable.

Keywords: Pickering Emulsion, Nanocomposite, Bacterial Cellulose, Foam, Renewable

INTRODUCTION

Research efforts are being focused on the development of environmentally friendly bio-based nanocomposites in the desire to seek alternatives to petroleum-based composites. In this work, novel bio-nanocomposite foams made from soybean-based resins and hydrophobised nanocellulose have been produced, which have potential in the manufacture of large composite parts, for example in cores for sandwich structures. Emulsion templating has emerged as an effective route to prepare porous polymer foams with a well-defined morphology since the latter is defined by the structure of the emulsion template at the gel-point of the polymerisation. Typically water-in-oil (w/o) emulsions are stabilised against droplet coalescence using large amounts (~20 vol.%) of structurally parasitic suitable non-ionic surfactants [1], which must be removed during post-processing. Pickering emulsions are emulsions that are solely stabilised by small particles. These emulsions are extremely stable due to the irreversible adsorption of particles at the interface between the dispersed and continuous phase. In this work we apply nano-fibrils derived from bacterial cellulose as Pickering emulsion stabilisers. Bacterial cellulose is attractive as a source of renewable nano-fibrils [2]; unlike wood-based cellulose it has the advantage of being free from lignin, hemicellulose and pectin. It is also inherently nano-sized, with fibrils of diameters ranging between 10 nm to 100 nm, it has a highly organised hierarchical structure resulting in high crystallinity (~90%) and possesses a high Young's modulus, reported as 114 GPa [3]. Bacterial cellulose has a highly hydrophilic character due to the many hydroxyl groups on the

surface and has been reported to stabilise oil-in-water emulsions [4]. The cellulose nano-fibrils must be hydrophobised to be compatible with many polymers and to act as stabilisers to form water-in-oil emulsions [5]. In this work we apply functionalised triglyceride oils as a monomer phase, which can be polymerised to high molecular weights and high cross-linking densities. The mechanical properties of soybean-, linseed- and castor-oil-based thermosetting polymers have been shown to be comparable to petroleum based unsaturated polyester resins [6-8]. We provide evidence that it is possible to stabilise Pickering medium internal phase emulsions (Pickering-MIPes) of functionalised soybean oils having internal aqueous phase levels above 60% solely with hydrophobised nanocellulose fibrils or oleic acid modified titania nanoparticles. Such emulsions can be used as emulsion templates for the synthesis of porous polymer foams, so-called poly-Pickering-MIPes if the components of the continuous phase are polymerisable.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Materials

Bacterial cellulose was extracted from *nata-de-coco*, a commercially available product, CHAOKOH[®] coconut gel in syrup (Thep. Padung Porn Coconut Co. Ltd, Bangkok, Thailand). Oleic acid functionalised titania nano-particles were produced in our labs, as previously described [9]. Acrylated epoxidized soybean oil (AESO), chloro(dimethyl)isopropylsilane (CDMIPS) (97% purity), imidazole (99% purity), toluene (99.8% purity), cumene hydroperoxide solution (~80% in cumene), toluene (99.8% purity), methanol (99.8% purity), acetone (99.8% purity) and tetrahydrofuran (THF) (99.9% purity) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Poole, UK). All reagents were used without further purification.

Extraction and purification of bacterial cellulose from *nata-de-coco*

Bacterial cellulose was extracted from *nata-de-coco*, by first rinsing the food product three times with dH₂O, the product was then sieved, homogenised and blended using a variable speed laboratory blender operated at maximum speed (Waring Laboratory, Essex, UK). The bacterial cellulose was then purified by boiling a concentration of 0.6 w/v % in 0.1M NaOH at 80° C for 2 h to remove any remaining microorganisms and soluble polysaccharides [10]. Bacterial cellulose was successively centrifuged (15 000 g), homogenised and rinsed to neutral pH.

Preparation of hydrophobic cellulose nano-fibrils via silylation

The cellulose was hydrophobised by adapting protocols developed by Goussé et al. [11,12] and Andresen et al. [5], slightly modified to suit our application. Bacterial cellulose fibrils in aqueous suspension (0.3%, w/v) were solvent exchanged into toluene through acetone first, then methanol. The reagent chloro(dimethyl)isopropylsilane (CDMIPS) was added at a molar ratio of 4:1 with respect to the repeating glucose units

of the bacterial cellulose [5]. Imidazole was added equimolar to CDMIPS to drive the reaction and trap the HCl released. During the silylation procedure, the CDMIPS reacts with the hydroxyl groups of the cellulose resulting in hydrophobisation of its surface. The reaction mixture was agitated using an orbital shaker (600 rpm) for 16 h prior to centrifugation (15 000 g) and decantation. Afterwards, a mix of methanol and THF (20:80, v/v) was added to dissolve the imidazolium chloride by-product and any disilylethers that may have formed, followed by centrifugation and decantation to obtain a modified cellulose plug. Dispersions of hydrophobised bacterial cellulose in AESO were obtained after rinsing twice with THF and successive centrifugation and re-dispersion operations to exchange the THF with toluene, and exchange of toluene with AESO. In order to produce films (described below) of the silylated cellulose, the fibrils were solvent exchanged back to water, through methanol using the aforementioned washing and centrifugation technique.

Characterisation of silylated bacterial cellulose nano-fibrils

Films of modified or unmodified bacterial cellulose were formed by taking some centrifuged sample (ca. 1g equivalent dry weight), rolling and pressing this in between release film to remove the water. The films were near fully dried in a hot press (George E. Moore and Sons, Birmingham, UK) and then pressed at 100 °C and 50 kN for 5 minutes, then dried in a vacuum oven over night. The wettability of cellulose films was determined by contact angle analysis using a Drop Shape Analyser (DSA 10 MK2, Krüss, Germany). Advancing contact angles were measured by increasing the volume of water droplets placed on the cellulose films in the range 2 µl – 20 µl at a rate of 6.32 µl min⁻¹ using a motorised syringe. At least six independent determinations at different sites for each sample were made. To determine the Zeta (ζ)-potential of the silylated and unmodified bacterial cellulose films the Electrokinetic Analyser (EKA, Anton Paar KG, Graz, Austria) based on the streaming potential method was used, in combination with a 2D film-measuring cell. pH-Dependent ζ-potential measurements were performed in 1m M KCl supporting electrolyte solution, while varying pH of solution with either 0.1 M HCl or 0.1 M KOH using a remote titration unit (RTU, Anton Paar KG, Graz, Austria) at a constant temperature of 20 °C. The modification was also characterised using FTIR. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was conducted on chromium sputter coated samples (sputtered for 1 min at 75 mA).

Preparation and characterisation of water-in-AESO emulsions stabilised by bacterial cellulose nano-fibrils

Between 10-15 ml of AESO was added into Falcon™ tubes (50 ml capacity), containing 0.5-5 wt.% silylated bacterial cellulose with respect to the AESO phase. The mixtures were homogenised in an ice bath to prevent premature polymerisation of the AESO at 20 000 rpm (using a Polytron PT10-35 GT batch homogeniser, Kinematica, Switzerland with a 9 mm rotor) for 1 min to disperse the cellulose nano-fibrils, prior to drop-wise addition of the aqueous phase, which contained 0.3M CaCl₂ · 2H₂O. Homogenisation was continued for a further minute after addition of the aqueous phase. Samples of the

emulsions were then taken and dripped into water to determine the emulsion type. The time dependent emulsion volume to the total volume of the water and oil phases (the emulsion stability index) was assessed over a 3-day period.

Preparation of polyAESO foams synthesised from emulsion templates, stabilised solely with hydrophobised bacterial cellulose

The emulsion templates (described above) were polymerised by addition of 3 wt.% of initiator cumene hydroperoxide (relative to the organic phase) to the AESO immediately prior to the emulsion formation (the aqueous phase addition is described above). The Falcon™ tubes were then capped and placed in an oven at 80° C for 24 h. The polymerised samples were then removed from the tubes and dried *in vacuo* at 80° C for a further 24 h.

Preparation of polyAESO foams synthesised from emulsion templates, stabilised solely with oleic acid functionalised titania nano-particles

The water-in-AESO emulsions were produced as described above using 1 wt.% oleic acid functionalised titania nano-particles, relative to the organic phase. The titania particles were used in place of hydrophobised bacterial cellulose nano-fibrils.

Mechanical characterisation of polyAESO foams

Compression tests were carried out using a Lloyds universal testing machine (Lloyds EZ50, Lloyds Instruments Ltd., Fareham, UK). Four samples (25 mm diameter and 10 mm high) were compressed at a loading rate of 1 mm min, by means of a compression plate equipped with a 50 kN load cell, until a displacement of 5 mm of the initial test piece thickness was attained. The elastic modulus was determined from the initial slope of the stress–strain plot.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Nano-fibril modification

The effect of modification (hydrophobisation) of the bacterial cellulose can be seen from FTIR spectroscopy (Figure 1), which confirms the successful silylation of the cellulose, with characteristic peaks at 855 cm⁻¹ (Si-C stretch), 833 cm⁻¹ (Si-CH₃ stretching) and 777 cm⁻¹ (Si-CH₃ rocking) [5,11,12], which were not present in the unmodified sample. Analysis of the surface by contact angle and streaming ζ-potential f (pH) measurement (Figures 2 and 3, respectively) clearly demonstrate a reduction in the hydroxyl groups at the surface and that the surface has been rendered hydrophobic. Water-in-air advancing contact angles on the silylated bacterial cellulose nano-fibril surface were recorded at 105 ± 2° and at 11 ± 3° on the unmodified cellulose surface. Contact angles of > 90° (measured through water) characterise hydrophobic particles and allow them to be adsorbed at the interface, stabilising w/o emulsions; the converse is true if this angle is < 90° [13]. ζ-Potential analysis confirms this as the plateau value

is shifted to increasingly lower values due to the reduction in hydroxyl groups at the surface (Figure 3).

Figure 1. FTIR spectra of unmodified bacterial cellulose and silylated bacterial cellulose.

Figure 2. Water-in-air contact angle on (L) an unmodified bacterial cellulose nano-fibril film and (R) on a silylated bacterial cellulose nano-fibril film.

Figure 3. ζ -Potential of unmodified bacterial cellulose and silylated cellulose as a function of pH.

PolyAESO foams synthesised from emulsion templates

Emulsions containing 50 or 60 vol.% aqueous dispersed phase containing 0.5-2 wt.% nano-fibrils relative to the organic phase exhibited emulsion stability indices of > 95 % after 3 days; the sample formulated with 60 vol.% aqueous phase and stabilised with 0.5 wt.% nano-fibrils exhibited some droplet coalescence in the centre of the emulsified volume, evident by a visible change in opacity. Emulsions containing aqueous phase levels > 70 vol.% became unstable within 0.5 h, creaming into an o/w phase at the top, with a water phase at the bottom; increasing the cellulose loading increased the creamed volume and stability. This creaming effect may have been due to over stirring using the homogeniser. It was not possible to prepare stable emulsions with > 4 wt.% hydrophobised bacterial cellulose loadings relative to the organic phase (with < 40 vol.% organic phase) due to flocking of cellulose fibrils and an inability to introduce enough shear. The polymerisation of the continuous phase of emulsions containing 50 and 60 vol.% aqueous dispersed phase and nano-fibril loadings of 0.5-2 wt.% relative to the organic phase, resulted in closed celled polymer foams (Figure 4). The majority of pores were in the range 10-300 μm diameter, with a mean of 80 μm . Polymerising the AEOS phase results in foams bio-nanocomposite foams with porosities up to 75%; the hydrophobised nano-cellulose adsorbs irreversibly at the water-oil interface and acts to sterically hinder droplet coalescence. The foam produced from the polymerised continuous phase of emulsion formulation stabilised by 1 wt.% silylated nano-fibrils with an internal aqueous phase of 50 vol.% exhibited a porosity of $76 \pm 1 \%$ which is likely to result from the presence of some air being beaten in during homogenisation, and some ejection of the continuous phase.

Figure 4. SEM of a poly-Pickering foam, formed from an emulsion formulated with 50 vol.% aqueous phase and stabilised with 1 wt.% silylated bacterial cellulose.

Oleic acid functionalised titania nano-particles also proved effective at stabilising 50 vol.% internal aqueous phase emulsions at just 1 wt.% loading with respect to the organic phase. The polyAESO foams synthesised from these stabilised emulsion templates are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. SEM of an AESO polyPickering foam formulated from an emulsion template containing 50 vol.% aqueous phase and 1 wt.% titania nano-particles with respect to the organic phase. Shown at low magnification (L) and at high magnification (R) the nano-particles can be seen lining the pore walls, where the water/oil interface was.

Mechanical properties of polyPickering AESO foams

The foams synthesised from emulsion templates containing 50 vol.% aqueous phase and 1 wt.% nano-fibrils exhibited a compressive modulus of 30 ± 5 MPa, with a specific modulus of 116 ± 11 kPa kg⁻¹ m³. These values are within the range of polymer foams of similar porosity produced from emulsion templates (with divinyl benzene and styrene mixed organic phases) that were stabilised by solely by 1 wt.% carbon nanotubes [14]. The polyMIPE synthesised from the emulsion template formulated from 50 vol.% aqueous phase stabilised by 1 wt.% titania nano-particles exhibited a porosity of $48 \pm 1\%$ and had a compressive modulus of 13 ± 4 MPa, with a specific modulus of 20 kPa kg⁻¹ m³.

CONCLUSIONS

Novel bio-based nanocomposite foams made from AESO and hydrophobised bacterial cellulose nano-fibrils have been produced using Pickering emulsion templating. Bacterial cellulose nano-fibrils hydrophobised either via silylation were able to stabilise water-in-modified natural oil emulsions. Oleic acid functionalised titania nano-particles were also able to stable these emulsions and polyPickering nanocomposite foams were produced. This technique will expand the applications and processing options available for renewable foams to produce large composite structures and sandwich cores, which can be formed *in situ*.

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